

TRANSLATION STRATEGIES AND TECHNIQUES

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Abstract: Various strategies, techniques and equivalence types play an essential role in the process of text translation, translation didactics and academic analysis of translation as a product. However, there is no agreement among the authors of influential theoretical works in Translation Studies about the meaning and scope of these key terms, so that the latter remain to some extent vague. This fact does not facilitate translation teachers' work and often causes chaos in discourse on translation. In this paper, an attempt will be made to defend the necessity of distinguishing between translation strategies and techniques, as well as preserving the concept of equivalence. Moreover, a quality analysis of selected terms will be conducted, inclusive of the arguments for their standardization. The study is directly focused on written translation but its conclusion may apply to interpreting, too.

Key words: Translation Studies, strategy, technique, equivalence, terminology.

1. Introduction

Most theorists make a distinction between a translation strategy and translation technique. However, the terminology they use for this purpose is far from uniform. In the most frequently cited works on this subject a strategy is sometimes referred to as a method (Vinay and Darbelnet 1995/1958, Newmark 1988) or global strategy (Lörscher 1991, 71, Jääskeläinen 1993), whilst a technique is mainly labelled a procedure (Newmark 1988, Delisle et al. 1999) or local strategy (Lörscher 1991, 71, Jääskeläinen 1993). Because of the misleading connotation of procedure as a complex, multistage process which does not always apply to translation (especially of a single word or phrase) in this paper the term technique is preferred. The comparison of provided definitions of translation methods and strategies on the one hand, and techniques and procedures on the other hand proves that both terms in each pair concord in content. According to Newmark, “[w]hile translation methods relate to whole texts, translation procedures are used for sentences and the smaller units of language“ (1988, 81). A similar distinction is made by Delisle et al. 8 (1999, 191, brackets removed) who observed that “[i]n contrast to translation strategies, which reflect the translator's global approach to a text, translation procedures are generally applied to individual text segments viewed as microcontexts”. As far as the notion of equivalence is concerned, it provokes so many controversies in Translation Studies that some scholars have declared it redundant (Snell-Hornby 1995/1988, Hermans 2007). Nevertheless, it continues to appear in research, and translation didactics could hardly do without it. It seems to be of a strategic nature and ensures a commonsense, honest approach to the essence of translation which is meant to preserve the identity of the original message within the bounds of possibility. This is worth noting in the times of progressing segmentation of research into translation and increasing vagueness of its subject.

2. Main part

Translation strategies

The online version of *Słownik Języka Polskiego* [The Dictionary of the Polish Language], which is likely to be consulted more often than the traditional paper volume, defines the concept of a strategy as “[an] excogitated plan of actions in a field” (translation mine).¹ This clearly implies that this term does not refer to a single action but rather a sequence of rational actions, taken on an analysis of a given situation. Therefore, in the case of translation as a complex task to be fulfilled, which concerns a certain text as a whole and aims to produce another text, a strategy can apply to the whole text only, and not to a single translator’s decision about the rendition of a particular lexical unit. Friedrich Schleiermacher (1815) already pointed to the two alternative translation strategies (although without using this term): moving the author towards the reader or the other way around. Later on, this opposition found numerous reformulations, in the shape Jiří Levy proposed in 1963 to discern between illusion and anti-illusion in literary translation. The former applied to translations that successfully imitated the natural use of the target language and could be mistaken for original products. The latter was reserved for the translations that can be easily recognised as such because traces of the original language were left there intentionally, for this purpose (2011/1963, 19-20). Lawrence Venuti (1995) introduced the pair of concepts domestication and foreignization, which correspond to the concept of a target text which is free of translation marks and without and with translation marks respectively (2008/1995, 15). Finally, Juliane House (1997) defined the terms covert and overt translation for the purposes of translation quality evaluation. In her view, covert translation is only recommendable in the case of culturally neutral texts, whilst the overt should be applied to those that are strongly embedded in the source culture (1997, 189-194). As can be seen, the abovementioned scholars articulate different aspects of translations, doing so from various angles. Schleiermacher expresses in the first place the translator’s perspective and choice between the author’s and reader’s interest. Levy adopts the recipient’s viewpoint and focuses on their overall experience based upon their experience with their own language. Venuti takes as the point of reference the abstract 1 horizon of the two cultures that are involved in the translation process. House emphasises the relationship between the source text and its culture as the decisive factor for the selection of translation strategy.

Certainly, the oppositions mentioned above do not exhaust the list of all the possible and actually employed translation strategies. The latter does not always have a matching opposing counterpart, and some appear controversial. Let us take what is called literal and free translation: On the one hand, they both might be qualified as internally contradictive since only a quotation with no intervention is truly literal, and a translation as such is never really free but always original-bound. On the other hand, it may be argued that any type of non-literal translation can be perceived as opposed to the latter. As mentioned at the beginning, not all researchers make a distinction between a translation strategy and technique (or procedure). *The Encyclopedia of Translation Studies* (2009/1988), edited by Mona Baker and Gabriela Saldanha does not include the translation technique (or procedure) as an entry, whilst the concept of a translation strategy is thoroughly presented from different angles (Kearns 2009/1998, 282-285). In her seminal book “In other words” (1992), which belongs to the canon of theoretical works on translation nowadays, Mona Baker herself (26-42) labels as strategies what is referred to in other sources as translation techniques or procedures (generalisation, neutralisation, cultural equivalent, borrowing or borrowing with explication, paraphrase or omission). A researcher can only recognise a translation strategy as such when they have studied and compared the whole source and target texts or at least extensive representative parts of them. What is more, any strategy may be absent from a bad translation. A strategy requires consistency and discipline of action, in translation and any other type of human activity. Like elsewhere, this rule is not always observed by performers, which should not really surprise. It is not difficult to note that the concept of a strategy, including translation strategies, is rather general and does not imply any particular actions to be taken in order to be carried out. These activities boil down to translation techniques which are employed in the linear process of target text

production. It is obvious that, regardless of the categories used by theoreticians in their translation process descriptions, in practice the translator is always looking for a suitable target language counterpart of a small, manageable text element: a word, phrase or a short sentence. While doing so, the translator applies, (depending on their experience, background and knowledge), more or less consciously, reliable and multiple described translation techniques that will be discussed below, in a selective approach.

3. Translation techniques

The abovementioned *Słownik Języka Polskiego* defines a procedure as “the specified rules of acting in a matter, usually of administrative or legal character” (translation mine).² The multiplicity of rules as well as the administrative or legal domain of their application have led me to definitely prefer using the term technique with reference to translation. Hejwowski (2015, 62) recommends banning the word procedure from translation-related terminology in a particularly convincing way. He quotes a definition of procedure that is slightly different from the above one and rightly adds that the scientific terms adopted from general lexicon should not be rendered into a meaning that contradicts their common understanding as ordinary words (Hejwowski 2015). For a technique, the already quoted *Słownik Języka Polskiego* offers two definitions that, in my opinion, capture the essence of the phenomenon under consideration best when combined together. A technique is explained there as (1) “a method” (in Polish: metoda) and (2) “a learned and practiced ability of performing certain activities”.³ Here, the notion of a method seems to better capture the essence of the locally applied technique than the sense of a strategy which refers to the text as a whole. Interestingly, *Mała Encyklopedia Przekładoznawstwa* (A Small Encyclopaedia of Translation Studies) by Dąbska-Prokop et al. (2000), the overall concept of which does not include a separate chapter on a translation technique or procedure, contains the term *procedure* (in Polish: procedura) in the index of terms (358), referring the reader to the chapter titled *Metodologia tłumaczenia* [Methodology of Translation], which is actually titled *Metodologia przekładu* 4 (134-139) and casually mentions the translation *technique* (in Polish: technika) (135). It would not make much sense to compile another list of translation techniques here since an interested reader can easily reach for detailed thematic

descriptions elsewhere (e.g. Newmark 1988, Kwieciński 2001, Molina and Hurtado Albir 2002). Instead, we shall focus on selected examples only, which seem controversial for different reasons. They either qualify for translation strategies rather than techniques, or serve the purpose of text manipulation rather than its translation, or account for the methods of lexicon expanding of the target language rather than those of forming texts on the grounds of the prototypes in other languages. They will be discussed in random order since it is not my purpose to suggest a ranking of the most unfit terms among the names of popular translation techniques.

III. Conclusions

Without the concept of equivalence, Translation Studies would be impossible because its very subject would get lost. It is the essence of translation to create a text concurring with the original in all possible respects. Only such a commonsense-based understanding of translation allows us to recognize other activities and products in translation, such as adaptation, localization or community interpreting which must not be confused with proper translation. Without the concept of equivalence, it is equally difficult to imagine translation didactics, where it constitutes the point of departure and reference, and finally the goal to be pursued. Despite the fact that equivalence can be most easily perceived at the level of word or sentence, it can be followed at the microtextual level too, where a combination of several sentences can be surveyed and memorized with no effort. Only the lack of equivalence on a microlevel entitles the researcher to question the equivalence of whole texts, but maybe it would make more sense to reserve this term for smaller units, remembering that limited applicability is not the same as no applicability. Translation techniques are not identical to

translation strategies. The former can be recognized any time, and the latter only on the analysis of entire texts, which seems logical since a technique is applied to a single sense unit and a strategy to the whole text. In this simple way, as suggested in this paper, translation techniques can be distinguished from translation strategies in research. In addition, it is the strategy chosen that suggests the techniques to be applied in translation, whilst it is the techniques that allow the researcher to reconstruct the translator’s strategies. Naturally, this reconstruction can succeed only if the translator acted on any strategies, which always happens in the case of good translations; that is to say, not all of them.

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